

Flexible pattern generation for phrenic nerve stimulation

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Abstract: Automatic phrenic nerve stimulation requires a sophisticated research of the patterns during stimulation. A stimulation system is presented which provides the necessary flexibility to generate stimulations with different patterns. The system enables quick changes during experiments. Initial tests of the stimulation system were performed on passive resistor-circuits with thoracic impedance values. The test results show that the stimulation system has the potential for in-vivo applications.

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I. Introduction

Phrenic nerve stimulation is used to artificially pace the diaphragm and was reported in treatment of quadriplegic patients [1] and central sleep apnea [2]. In mechanical ventilation, it was used to control the end-tidal carbon dioxide in rats with respiratory depression [3]. The current amplitude, but not the stimulation pattern was changed. However, the pattern may influence the quality of the stimulation. Therefore, a stimulation system was developed with the goal to systematically analyze stimulation patterns and quickly change algorithm parameters during in-vivo experiments.

II. Material and methods

An overview of the stimulation system is given in Fig. 1. A PC running Matlab 2019b (The MathWorks Inc., Natick, USA) and dSPACE Control Desk 7.1 (dSPACE GmbH, Paderborn, Germany) communicates over an Ethernet connection with a real time PC (MicroLabBox, dSPACE). The real time PC communicates with the stimulator via the serial peripheral interface (SPI), which is transferred through medically graded digital isolators (ADuM2400 / ADuM2401, Analog Devices, Inc., Wilmington, U.S.A.) for safety. Using SPI, a digital-analog-converter (DAC, DAC80508, Texas Instruments Incorporated, Dallas, U.S.A.) generates a programmable analog voltage V_{DAC} between zero and five volts. V_{DAC} is fed into an operational amplifier (LM324, Texas Instruments Incorporated) in a noninverting circuit to generate the amplified voltage V_{Amp} . V_{Amp} is lead to an H-bridge (NCV7535_D) with which the direction of the output voltage V_{Out} can be changed for biphasic stimulation. The output of the H-bridge is connected to the stimulation electrodes.

Through a small resistor and a bidirectional current sensing amplifier (INA190A2, Texas Instruments Incorporated) the stimulation current I_{stim} is converted into a measurement voltage V_I . V_I is the input of the analog-digital-converter (ADC, DS1018, Texas Instruments Incorporated), where the current measurements can be read out via SPI by the real time PC.

Figure 1: Overview of the stimulation system. The stimulator consists of the blocks inside the dashed lines. The double headed arrows indicate communication; the single headed arrows signal flow.

Apart from the ADC, V_I is used in the overcurrent protection circuit. The DAC generates the programmable threshold voltages $V_{I,min}$ and $V_{I,max}$. V_I , $V_{I,min}$ and $V_{I,max}$ are the inputs of a window comparator. The window comparator output enables the H-bridge. Therefore, the H-bridge output is enabled if and only if the equation

$$V_{I,min} < V_I < V_{I,max} \quad (1)$$

holds. This safety mechanism guarantees that under no circumstances the current gets larger than the currents specified by the threshold voltages.

As there are two phrenic nerves, one on the left side and one on the right side of the body, the introduced circuit is partly duplicated, such that the stimulation system has four output ports for stimulation electrodes.

The programming of the real time PC is performed in MATLAB Simulink[®] and MATLAB Stateflow[®]. Due to the nonlinear behavior of the operational amplifier lookup tables

were used to describe the relation between V_{DAC} and V_{Amp} . The lookup tables were determined by measurements of V_{Amp} while V_{DAC} was set for both output stages. The relationship between I_{stim} and V_1 was measured and showed a linear dependency with an offset voltage. The offset voltage is given by the voltage V_{ref} from an external reference voltage (LM4040, Texas Instruments Incorporated). Since V_{ref} may change over time, the measurement of V_1 is calibrated in dSPACE Control Desk while the H-bridge is not enabled, such that I_{stim} must be zero at the time of calibration.

The software can set the train rate, the train duration, the stimulation pulse width, the pulse direction, the time between pulses, the start voltage, the maximum voltage and the voltage slew rate. These settings are programmed as user inputs on the PC in dSPACE Control Desk such that they can be changed quickly during experiments. A table with various stimulation patterns was created for systematic analysis.

III. Results and discussion

In an ongoing animal study the stimulation system will be tested in a porcine model. Initial tests were performed with a passive resistor-capacitor circuit as shown in Fig. 2. The impedances Z_1 and Z_2 comprise the impedance of integrated circuits and an internal resistance of 1690 Ω . The internal resistance was added to limit the absolute current regardless of the dynamic current limits of the window comparator. The measured resistance of the used electrodes is 1 Ω . The test circuit is built with passive components that match closely a model of the thoracic impedance reported in [4].

Figure 2: Test setup of the stimulation system.

Fig. 3 shows the set voltage for one pulse train sequence given by the following stimulation settings: 5ms pulse width, biphasic stimulation, 2ms pause between pulses, 2 V start voltage, 10 V maximum voltage and 16 V/s voltage slew rate. Fig. 4 shows the corresponding measured current. The maximum current is 5.5 mA in positive and 5.8 mA in negative direction. The current between stimulation pulses is 0.1 mA.

The difference between the maximum currents in positive and negative direction is assumed to be caused by the asymmetry in the test circuit. The 0.1 mA current can be explained by leakage currents as they occur even when no electrodes are connected to the stimulator. The current shown in fig. 4 behaves accordingly to the expected result as it increases proportionally to the voltage.

Figure 3: Set voltage during the test stimulation.

Figure 4: Measured current during the test stimulation.

IV. Conclusions

A stimulation system for phrenic nerve stimulation has been presented. Stimulation patterns and voltage amplitudes can be changed flexibly. An initial test with a thoracic impedance model made of resistors and capacitors has been shown. In future, various stimulation patterns will be tested to find the optimal stimulation patterns and voltage amplitudes in animal tests.

AUTHOR'S STATEMENT

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